

Data and Project Guide

Vector-Based Analysis of Phonetic Iconicity in Spatial Dimension

Adjectives in Yunnan Minority Languages

Purpose of This Document

This guide provides an overview of the project structure and directs readers to the appropriate resources based on their needs. It is intended as the entry point for all users of this research output.

Project Structure Overview

The project is organized into two main directories, each serving a distinct purpose:

Project Root/

— Data_and_Results/	# Core research data and findings
— Supporting_Materials/	# Complete workflow and code repository
— SDAs_Tool/	# All Python scripts and detailed documentation
— README.md	# Project overview and pipeline description
— README_WORKFLOW.md	# Detailed workflow documentation
— README_DATA_FORMAT.md	# Data format specifications
— ...	
— SDAs_Data/	# Raw output from workflow
— yunnan_languages_SDAs/	# CLDF dataset
— soundvectors_Data	# soundvectors data

Directory Details and Usage

1. Data_and_Results

This directory contains all core data and analytical results from the study, can be direct approach by all readers.

Contents:

- ◆ Data Catalog and Description.docx: A comprehensive catalog and detailed description of all data files in this directory.
- ◆ 1. Language Samples/: Background information for 36 languages.
- ◆ 2. Language Materials/: Original IPA transcriptions of spatial adjectives.
- ◆ 3. Vector data/: Numerical vector representations of phonemes.
- ◆ 4. Word pair vectors/: Difference vectors for antonym pairs.
- ◆ 5. Calculation for Principal Component Analysis (PCA)/: Results from dimensionality reduction.
- ◆ 6. PCA contribution data/: Analysis of key phonetic feature contributions.
- ◆ 7. SSP data/: Sonority Sequencing Principle data.
- ◆ 8. Trustworthiness data/: Evaluation of methodological reliability.
- ◆ Plot all/: All visualizations, including heatmaps, scatter plots, and fitted plane diagrams.

For readers who wish to examine the findings, visualizations, and processed data without engaging with the complete workflow.

2. Supporting_Materials

This directory contains the complete workflow required to reproduce the analysis from the original data.

Contents:

- ◆ SDAs_Tool/: All Python scripts for the analysis pipeline. This subdirectory contains three detailed documentation files:
 - README.md: Overview of the project and analysis pipeline.
 - README_WORKFLOW.md: Detailed step-by-step workflow documentation for all processing stages.
 - README_DATA_FORMAT.md: Complete specifications for all data formats used in the project.
- ◆ SDAs_Data/: Complete raw output generated by executing the analysis scripts.
- ◆ yunnan_languages_SDAs: CLDF dataset containing:
 - languages.csv: Language basic information
 - parameters.csv: Semantic parameter definitions
 - forms.csv: IPA forms of words (including segments)
 - metadata.json: Dataset metadata
- ◆ soundvectors_Data/: vectors generated by soundvectors and the statistic results.
- ◆ Vector data files: Initial phonetic vectors used as input to the pipeline.
- ◆ Mapping files: Feature and language mapping tables for data interpretation.

For readers who intend to replicate the study, modify the analysis, or inspect the computational methods in detail.

Data Flow

Supporting_Materials/SDAs_Tool/ (scripts + documentation)

↓ (execution)

Supporting_Materials/SDAs_Data/ (raw output)

↓ (processing and organization)

Data_and_Results/ (curated results)

Quick Start Guide

If you are a reader focusing on results:

1. Begin with the visualizations in Data_and_Results/plot_all/.
2. Consult the Data Catalog and Description.doc within Data_and_Results/ for an in-depth understanding of any specific dataset.
3. Refer to folders 1-8 within Data_and_Results/ for the underlying data corresponding to your area of interest.

If you are a reader focusing on methods and reproducibility:

1. Navigate to the Supporting_Materials/ directory.

2. Review the documentation files within Supporting_Materials/SDAs_Tool/:
 - For an overview: README.md
 - For workflow details: README_WORKFLOW.md
 - For data format specifications: README_DATA_FORMAT.md
3. Examine the original data in yunnan_languages_SDAs/ and the vector files in the root of Supporting_Materials/.
4. Examine or execute the scripts within Supporting_Materials/SDAs_Tool/ to regenerate the analysis.
5. Find raw script outputs in Supporting_Materials/SDAs_Data/.

Data Access

The dataset for this study is available via the open-access repository:

Zenodo: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20478887> (Version V5)